

Next Generation BiOactive NAnocoatings - NOVA

NOVA: preventing the transmission of infectious diseases in everyday life.

Medical devices

"high-touch" surfaces

Textiles

Masks

Waiting rooms

Restrooms

Pastic and glass

→ Safe and sustainable from synthesis to end-of-life coatings.

→ Novel antimicrobial test methods for real-life and operational conditions.

→ Robust in-silico models for risk management and coating development.

→ Advanced coating instruments.

Next generation contact killing and light-activated antimicrobial coatings

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under grant agreement number 101058554. This work was co-funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee grant number 10042534 & grant number 10055606.

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Zenodo
Community!

Or visit our
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Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation